

IoT Enabled Bluetooth Controlled Advanced Agricultural Robot

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ABSTRACT

The project report outlines the development of an IoT-based, Bluetooth-controlled agricultural robot. This innovative robot addresses critical agricultural challenges by emphasizing efficiency, cost reduction, and sustainability. Powered by an Arduino UNO microcontroller, it communicates with a mobile app via Bluetooth. Key functionalities include precise seed sowing using a servo motor, automated soil management for digging and closing soil during sowing, an intelligent watering system triggered by a moisture sensor, and grass cutting capabilities. By demonstrating the potential of IoT and robotics, this project paves the way for precision farming and sustainable practices in agriculture.

Keywords: smart farming, Artificial intelligence, Internet of Things, sensors.

1. Introduction

The IoT-based agricultural robot represents a groundbreaking solution for modern farming challenges. By integrating IoT technologies and robotics, this project aims to enhance efficiency, reduce Labor costs, and promote sustainability in agriculture. Powered by an Arduino UNO microcontroller and utilizing Bluetooth communication, the robot offers essential functionalities for farming operations. These include precise seed sowing, automated soil management, intelligent watering based on soil moisture levels, grass cutting, and remote control via a dedicated mobile application. Through this synergy of IoT and robotics, the initiative underscores the potential for transformative change in the agricultural sector. By championing precision farming, resource optimization, and sustainable practices, the agricultural robot promises improved efficiency and advancements in agricultural methodologies [1-3].

Additionally, the project emphasizes the importance of weed removal as a key function. Weeds compete with crops for vital resources such as nutrients, water, and sunlight, making weed removal crucial for optimizing agricultural practices. The robot's ability to address this challenge contributes significantly to efficient and effective farming operations [4-6].

Furthermore, the real-time soil moisture level detection provided by the intelligent watering system plays a pivotal role in overcoming agricultural challenges [7]. By collecting and analysing data on environmental factors, this innovative robot empowers farmers to make informed decisions, ultimately promoting sustainable and efficient farming practices. [8&9].

1.1 Experimental Setup

The system uses a variety of sensors and components to manage the irrigation, seeding, and grass cutting. The system starts with a battery that supplies power to the entire system. An Arduino Uno, a microcontroller board, is the central processing unit that controls the different parts of the system. A moisture sensor detects the level of moisture in the soil. When the moisture level falls below a certain point, the sensor sends a signal to the Arduino Uno. The Arduino Uno then activates a water pump via a motor driver, which supplies water to the garden. A Bluetooth module allows the user to communicate with the system and potentially adjust settings. A servo motor appears to be used for seed sowing.

Fig.1 Methodology of project.

Fig.2 Circuit diagram

Fig.3 User interface

2. Circuit Diagram

Figure 2 shows upon power supply, the Arduino Uno connects to the Bluetooth module. The mobile application pairs with the Arduino Uno to control the model. The operation relies on mobile controllers, denoted as F (Front), L (Left), R (Right), B (Back). Six motors connected to L298DR motor drives facilitate movement according to controller inputs. The water pump, controlled by the Z button, activates based on soil moisture sensor readings. Unwanted weeds are removed automatically during operation. Seed sowing is initiated using the Y button. All operations are managed manually through the mobile application, ensuring effective functionality.

3. User Interface

Shown Below is a diagram which shows the interface of the app. The app shown has 5 buttons and all the button gives 5 different bytes in the output that is to be fed to the microcontroller to further process. For e.g. if we press Up! Button, the Bluetooth module will give 1 byte at its output.

Z: Water Pump On/Of

Y: Start Sowing

y: Stop Sowing

I: Precise Left Turn

F: Move Forward

r: Precise Right Turn

R: Move Right

n: Stop Weed Removing

B: Move Backward

m: Start Weed Moving

L: Move Left

4. Results And Discussion

OPERATIONS

Weed Removal:

Our innovative weed removal technology offers precise and efficient control, minimizing environmental impact and promoting sustainable farming practices.

Soil Moisture level Detection:

Our agricultural robot monitors soil moisture levels with precision, optimizing watering schedules for maximum yield and promoting sustainable water management practices.

Seed sowing:

Our agricultural robot revolutionizes seed sowing controlled remotely via Bluetooth for enhanced productivity and sustainability.

Water Supply:

Our agricultural robot prioritizes soil moisture maintenance and efficient nutrient delivery, empowering farmers with real-time control to optimize crop nutrition and promote sustainable farming practices for a resilient agricultural future.

Fig.4 IoT Enabled Bluetooth Controlled Advanced Agriculture Robot

5. Conclusions

This study addresses the gap in understanding the practical applicability and socio-economic impact of smart agricultural technologies, aiming to facilitate their effective adoption and implementation. By developing smart solutions like soil moisture monitoring sensors, smartphone-operated weed-cutting robots, and Bluetooth-controlled pesticide spraying systems, we tackle key challenges in farming such as lack of mechanization, small land-holdings, and inefficient biocide use, paving the way for revolutionizing farming practices, promoting sustainability, and enhancing productivity.

Future enhancements include integrating fertilizer spraying and obstacle avoidance, aiming to continuously improve farming practices and contribute to sustainability.

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